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Research Article

**A COMPARATIVE STUDY ON HABITS AND ACADEMIC
ACHIEVEMENTS ON THE 2ND YEAR AND FINAL YEAR MBBS
STUDENTS: MUHAMMAD MEDICAL COLLEGE,
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Article Received: June 2019**Accepted:** July 2019**Published:** August 2019**Abstract:**

This comparative academic research work was carried out at MMC (Muhammad Medical College), Mirpurkhas, Sindh during April 2018 to May 2018 session on 2nd and 5th year (The final year) MBBS students. Information was obtained on questionnaire regarding study habits of students and academic achievements. There were 109 participant 50 from 2nd year MBBS and 59 students were from 5th and final year. The examination department was approached for the results of the above students in their previous year. We found stronger association 94.3% and significant difference-0.002 between the study habits as well as academic achievements between the 2nd and final year students.

Conclusion: *Academic achievements are strongly associated with study habits and the students of final year are more managed as compared to 2nd year students.*

Key Words: *Study achievements. Study questionnaire, Study habits,*

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INTRODUCTION:

Academia in recent years has evolved to become more of a science than an art. Researchers are conducting studies for the development of all-encompassing techniques that effectively improve the academic performance of individuals. Such techniques are known as study skills. A person possesses the ability to inculcate such study skills in other people this transferability of study skills allows us to conduct fruitful researches that result in pragmatic improvements in the field of academia [1]. Study styles refer to study habits, which are subject to human attitude and behavior. Martha study habits means the mood which is adopted by students as a study plan apart from the lecture attendance for knowledge purpose on any topic. They obviously vary from individual to individual according to their cognitive capability and personal preferences [2]. In essence, these study habits assist individuals in apprehending information more readily and determine their performance in examinations. Revision of study material, self-study, frequent sessions of repetition as well combined discussion study are examples of such habits [3,4]. Some researchers have shown that senior students with time and experience tend to develop better study habits leading to better results than junior students who lack these efficient study habits[5]. Study habits assist individuals in apprehending information more readily and determine their performance in examinations. Revision of study material, the frequency of study sessions, self-study, and combined study are examples of such habits[6-8]. The primary objective of this study is to analyze the role of such study habits in senior and junior medical students in the context of academic achievement and to identify the best study habits. Unfortunately, there is a surprising lack of research with reference to habits of study among the students of medical sciences in Pakistan, and therefore, this study aims to contribute towards existing literature by means of exploring the relationship between study habits and academic achievement of medical students in MMC, LUMHS. The objective for this research was to compare level of study habits and achievements in junior and senior

students and to identify the best study habits among the two classes.

METHODS:

The students of 2nd along with 5th year of MBBS at Muhammad Medical College were included, excluding the other classes. Total 109 students were evaluated 59 from the final year while 50 from the 2nd year. Data obtained in the form of questionnaire based on section one, demographic data like name, class, roll number, and gender and section two contain 14 questions about study habits having 5 option categories like strongly agree having 3 points, agree having 2 points, neutral given no point, disagree option had -2 points while -1point was given to strongly disagree option . Questions were about student's knowledge regarding good and bad habits of study, trend of studies, their way of study management and how habits help in good academic achievements. The analyzed of data was performed SPSS at significance level of 0.05.

RESULTS:

Pearson Correlation 0.943 showed strong association among the two variables (94.3% relationship) p-value is 0.000. Second year and final years students were compared and found that the mean value of 2nd year students is 0.8900- which is deviated from 0.85821 units. On the other hand the value of mean for the final year students is 1.4407 however it is deviated from 0.9247 units. From the analysis of mean values it can be said that the academic achievement of 5th year students is higher than the 2nd year medical students. There were 50 respondents belonging to the 2nd year and 59 students from the final year MBBS. We wanted to analyze if there was any significant difference between the study habits of 2nd year MBBS students and 5th year MBBS students. It is evident that from the p-value given in the above table that there is a significant difference as the value is 0.002. Based on the results it can be said that the study habits are not consistent for both the 2nd year MBBS students and final year MBBS students and the final year students performed better than the 2nd year students.

Table 1: Relationship b/w academic achievements and study habits

Correlations			
		Study Habits	Academic Achievements
Study Habits	Pearson Correlation	1	.943**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	109	109
Academic Achievements	Pearson Correlation	.943**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	109	109

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

. TABLE 2:

Group Statistics					
	Academic Year	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Academic Achievements	2nd Year	50	.8900	.85821	.12137
	5th Year	59	1.4407	.92474	.12039

Table 3:

Independent Samples Test										
		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Academic Achievements	Equal variances assumed	.278	.599	-3.201	107	.002	-.55068	.17202	-.89168	-.20968
	Equal variances not assumed			-3.221	106.092	.002	-.55068	.17095	-.88960	-.21175

DISCUSSION:

The findings of the study identified the relationship between study habits of various students and their respective academic achievements. It realizes the fact that the patterns of behaviour and efforts with respect to studies contribute as learning guidelines for students to succeed academically. We found that there are various factors that determine academic performance of students, particularly in the medical field; these include personality traits, prior academic credentials, and disparate learning strategies. Previously positive relationship was published for study habits, learning and achievements in health sciences education[9-11]. The study helps us realize that academic achievements serve as the necessary motivator to maintain a constant academic and professional growth. Not only do they provide you with the credentials to achieve future success but also instil a sense of accomplishment in students. Thus, students constantly strive to achieve better grades at every stage of the learning process[12-14]. The amount of skills and knowledge that is being acquired over a period of time in a particular area of study are termed as academic achievements. There exist several factors that influence the academic achievements and learning outcomes of a student[14-15]. The responses of the study claimed that if a student adopts healthy study habits such as studying regularly, making and reviewing notes, participating and attentively listening in class, working with planning and organisation, and reading textbooks, then the student is likely to succeed and develop skills and gain knowledge successfully during the learning

process which increase with time. Baeten et al (2010) reported that if a student possesses unfavourable study habits such as lack of punctuality in completing work, excessive involvement in extracurricular activities, low attendance, and irregularity in studying inhibit intellectual growth and makes students perform incompetently in their examinations[13]. This prevents them from attaining academic achievement in his/her academic life. Students in early years of medical college tend to lag behind by displaying these traits¹⁴. With a change in objectives and an increase in academic workload, new students find it difficult to adapt to an unfamiliar atmosphere of a college or university. Thus, students are required to adopt new ways of learning, strategies, and study habits that would assist students in attaining their ambitions in this new environment^{14,15}. These habits include ample study hours, high attendance, exploring textbooks, prior preparation of examinations, studying environment, studying in groups, not using social media during study period and to concentrate fully on the subject. All these factors are considered as good habits of a student. Students who observe the above and attend classes regularly and do not bunk any class and perform effectively in the learning programmes and activities of the class are likely to achieve excellent academic achievements and their performance is much better than those who do not attend the classes regularly and adopt the above mentioned study habits [16,17]. Responses of the students also identified that effective habits of a student enable him/her to work at his/her optimum

level of efficiency. The partakers realized the values of good lecture attendance on student's performance [18]. Student of final year were aware about entering the practical world in near future, with not much time to waste anymore tend to perform better displaying better study habits[19]. Students having good abilities of learning are considered to have high level of involvement in their educational process, and evaluating their tasks that they are supposed to complete in an effective manner. Senior students try for higher intellectual abilities, evaluate and sustain their study habits, and cautiously weigh the factors that impact on their learning and achievement[20]. Showing interest in your subject is found to be an essential psychological trait that not only affects the study habits and patterns but also contribute in other facets of life such as academic as well as professional development of the students[21]. Thus, student's study habits have a direct relationship with their academic achievement and the sooner a student specially a medical student realizes this, it would be better for them in their academic performance not only in the college but throughout life.

CONCLUSION:

We conclude strong association between academic achievements and study habits. We observed significant difference between 2nd year students and final year students.

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